

THEORETICAL AND APPLIED ISSUES IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS AND LITERATURE: STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS, EDUCATIONAL CHALLENGES, AND LITERARY INTERPRETATION.

Mavlonova Sevinch, 1 course student of TerSPI.

Scientific Supervisors: Teacher of the Department of Russian Language and

Literature at TerSPI, Oromidinova Dildora Pardabayevna

Teacher of the Department of Practical English at TerSPI, Morozova Anastasia

Vladimirovna

Annotation. This article provides an in-depth exploration of Uzbek linguistics and literature, emphasizing both traditional theoretical frameworks and modern applied approaches. Linguistic analysis examines the phonetic, morphological, and syntactic features of the Uzbek language, highlighting its unique characteristics as part of the Turkic language family. Literary analysis delves into Uzbek literature's historical and cultural significance, from its classical roots in the Timurid era to modern themes of national identity and social change.

Key words : uzbek linguistics and literature, language revolution, language identity, theoretical frameworks, language typology ,uzbek cultural heritage.

Аннотация. Эта статья представляет углублённое исследование узбекской лингвистики и литературы, уделяя внимание как традиционным теоретическим основам, так и современным прикладным подходам. Лингвистический анализ включает изучение фонетических, морфологических и синтаксических особенностей узбекского языка, подчёркивая его уникальные черты как части тюркской языковой семьи. В работе рассматривается историческое и культурное значение узбекской литературы — от её классических корней в эпоху Тимуридов до современных тем национальной идентичности и социальных перемен.

Ключевые слова: узбекская лингвистика и литература, языковая революция, языковая идентичность, теоретические основы, типология языков, узбекское культурное наследие.

Annotatsiya. Bu maqola o‘zbek tilshunosligi va adabiyotining chuqur tahlilini taqdim etadi, an’anaviy nazariy asoslar hamda zamonaviy amaliy yondashuvlarga e’tibor qaratadi. Tilshunoslik tahlili o‘zbek tilining fonetik, morfologik va sintaktik xususiyatlarini o‘rganishni o‘z ichiga oladi, uning turkiy til oilasining bir qismi sifatida o‘ziga xos xususiyatlarini ta’kidlaydi. Ishda o‘zbek adabiyotining tarixiy va madaniy ahamiyati ham ko‘rib chiqiladi — uning dastlabki davrlaridan hozirgi kungacha.

Kalit so‘zlar: O‘zbek tilshunosligi, adabiyot, tilshunoslik tahlili, fonetik xususiyatlar, morfologik xususiyatlar, sintaktik xususiyatlar, turkiy til oilasi, tarixiy ahamiyat, madaniy ahamiyat, o‘zbek adabiyoti

In recent decades, Uzbek linguistics and literary studies have been expanding to include both traditional theoretical frameworks and innovative applied approaches. This paper explores evolution. Additionally, it examines the applied challenges within language education and media, and concludes with a discussion on literary theory in Uzbek literature, emphasizing philosophical and cultural interpretations.

The Uzbek language, as part of the Turkic language family, possesses distinct phonetic, morphological, and syntactic features that define its linguistic identity. Phonetic characteristics, such as vowel harmony and consonant assimilation, are integral to understanding Uzbek's unique phonological system. Morphological studies further highlight agglutinative properties and case systems that distinguish Uzbek from Indo-European languages, providing a framework for understanding syntactic structures. By grounding these observations within linguistic theory, we can appreciate how Uzbek contributes to broader discussions in language typology. Language in Uzbekistan has been shaped significantly by socio-political developments, particularly following independence. National language policies, shifts in the writing system, and media have all influenced linguistic norms. The resurgence of Uzbek cultural identity has bolstered the preservation and promotion of Uzbek, often in contrast to Russian and other regional languages. This section reviews how political discourse and globalization impact Uzbek, affecting linguistic choices, identity, and standardization efforts.

Challenges in Applied Linguistics and Language Education

Applied linguistics in Uzbekistan faces distinct challenges and opportunities, especially in language education and media. With increasing demand for Uzbek language learning materials, digital resources have become invaluable for both learners and educators. Innovations in teaching methodology, such as interactive and digital platforms, are transforming the learning landscape. This section also examines the role of media as both a linguistic resource and a potential source of language erosion, discussing how applied linguistics can bridge these gaps to support sustainable language practices. Scientific and Theoretical Foundations in Uzbek Literature Uzbek literature provides an insightful lens through which national identity, history, and

philosophical questions are explored. Literary theories applied to Uzbek works reveal recurring themes and structures, including epic poetry forms, narrative devices, and symbolism. This section outlines the theoretical frameworks that scholars employ when analyzing Uzbek literature, highlighting genre theory and narrative strategies that place Uzbek literature within global literary discourse. Additionally, it examines the role of literature in reflecting and shaping social values.

Uzbek literature dates back over 1,000 years, with roots in the 9th to 12th centuries, influenced by Persian, Arabic, and Turkic literary traditions. The most prominent early works are from the Timurid era (14th-15th centuries). Classical Literature: Alisher Navoi (1441-1501) is considered the father of Uzbek literature. His "Khamsa" is a monumental work consisting of five epic poems, totaling over 50,000 lines of verse. Uzbek literature is written in a language that evolved from Chagatai, an Eastern Turkic language, with strong Persian and Arabic influences. Modern Uzbek, however, uses a simplified Turkic vocabulary, with Latin and Cyrillic script versions. Genres and Forms: Classical Uzbek literature primarily features poetry, with forms like the "ghazal," "qit'a," and "masnavi" dominating. The "aruz" metric system was widely used for its rhythmic structure. These forms remained popular until the 20th century. The 20th century saw a shift toward prose, especially after Uzbekistan's incorporation into the Soviet Union. Themes expanded to include socialism, independence, and national identity. Notable modern authors include Abdulla Qodiriy and Cholpon. Uzbek literature is widely taught in Uzbekistan's schools and universities, with a strong emphasis on Navoi's poetry. It remains a central component of the national education curriculum, promoting cultural heritage.

Uzbek literature is widely taught in Uzbekistan's schools and universities, with a strong emphasis on Navoi's poetry. It remains a central component of the national education curriculum, promoting cultural heritage. Key works of Uzbek literature have been translated into Russian, English, and Persian, expanding the global readership. Navoi's works, in particular, have been translated into more than 20 languages. Since the 1990s, themes of cultural identity and social change are prominent. Literary

festivals and awards in Uzbekistan celebrate contemporary literature, with increased participation from young writers.

Philosophical and National Elements in Literary Analysis

Analyzing Uzbek literary works through a philosophical and national lens unveils deeper meanings rooted in cultural identity and existential questions. The presence of national themes reflects a commitment to cultural preservation, while philosophical elements allow for universal resonance. This section addresses critical methodologies that uncover how national and philosophical themes reinforce one another, deepening readers' understanding of the cultural and intellectual dimensions of Uzbek literature.

The examination of both theoretical and applied issues in Uzbek linguistics and literature underscores the value of an interdisciplinary approach. By integrating structural linguistics with socio-political analysis, applied language challenges, and literary theory, researchers can gain a comprehensive understanding of Uzbek language and culture. Such a holistic perspective not only fosters greater appreciation for Uzbek's linguistic and literary contributions but also supports its development in a globalized world.

References

1. Crystal, D. (2003). *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language*. Cambridge University Press.
2. Fairclough, N. (2015). *Language and Power*. Routledge.
3. Gee, J.P. (2004). *An Introduction to Discourse Analysis: Theory and Method*. Routledge.
4. Сайфуллаев Нажибулло. (2023). ТЕРМИНЫ – НЕОТЪЕМЛЕМОЕ БОГАТСТВО НАШЕГО ЯЗЫКА. *PEDAGOGS*, 46(1), 67–69.
5. Halliday, M.A.K., & Matthiessen, C. (2014). *An Introduction to Functional Grammar*. Routledge.
6. Trudgill, P. (2000). *Sociolinguistics: An Introduction to Language and Society*. Penguin Books.oj